

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Analysing Personality Dimensions: Exploring Thinking vs. Feeling among MBA Students in Gujarat State

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Abstract

Objectives: The study explores the Thinking (T) and Feeling (F) personality traits of MBA students from selected Gujarati business schools. Understanding the relationships between these personality traits and demographic variables, including gender, education, and job experience, is the primary objective of the study. **Methods:** With a Cronbach's Alpha of 87%, the NERIS Type Explorer[®] Scale was adopted to survey 1,067 management students. To examine the data, descriptive statistics were used. Cluster sampling was utilized in this cross-sectional study to guarantee that students across Gujarat were equally represented. A structured questionnaire was used to gather demographic information, and the NERIS Type Explorer[®] Scale was used to evaluate personality traits. Frequency distribution, chi-square tests, and ANOVA were used to examine the data in order to find significant relationships between demographic characteristics and personality traits. **Findings:** According to the survey, 37.1% of respondents were associated with the Thinking (T) dimension, whereas 62.9% of respondents had a Feeling (F) personality. Personality traits and variables, including mother's education, gender, and previous job experience were shown to be significantly correlated. The Feeling (F) attribute was more prevalent among female students and those with less job experience. The results imply that management students of Gujarat state are more likely to make emotional decisions. **Novelty:** This study offers new insights on how occupational exposure and parental education influence management students' personality traits. It emphasizes how management programs at business schools must incorporate instruction in both logical thinking and emotional intelligence in order to equip students for making well-rounded decisions in leadership positions. In order to prepare students for leadership roles, the study highlights the necessity for management programs to strike a balance between teaching students logical thinking skills and emotional intelligence.

Keywords: Thinking, Feeling; T-F Personality; Personality Dimensions; Emotional Decision-Making

1 Introduction

Every individual in the world differs from each other. Each individual has an essential role in his or her life. Personality is the product of social interaction in group life. Through years' personality is observed as a practical force that results in success as well as failure in life. In our society, every individual has different traits like height, skin colour, weight, habits, physique, and attitudes. This can vary from every group and society. Individuals' perceptions, interactions, and reactions to their surroundings are greatly influenced by their personalities, particularly in professional and academic contexts. Every individual has a personality that could be very impressive or not. This is developed by socializing with the culture of a group and society. Variation in culture and time helps to determine the personality of an individual. Personality is the summation of an individual's total behaviour and includes intelligence, mentality, and interests. It is the combination of mental abilities, physical abilities, and capabilities of a person. Personality indicates a major part in organizational behaviour it shows various methods of a person thinking, feeling, and behave belongings various facets of the place of work. One's personality affects his/her behaviour in groups, approach, and the decision-making. A knowledge of how demographic variables, including gender, parental education, and previous job experience, impact these personality traits among management students in India is lacking, though, as the majority of current research focuses on Western contexts or generic business school populations. Understanding personality characteristics is essential for management students because they influence decision-making methods, leadership potential, and interpersonal effectiveness. Using the NERIS Type Explorer[®] paradigm, this study examines the Thinking (T) and Feeling (F) personality dimensions among MBA students in Gujarat, India. This study looks at how variables like parental education and previous work experience may affect students' cognitive and emotional choices, in contrast to other research that treats personality traits as static or context neutral. Gujarat's unique socioeconomic, educational, and cultural background offers a useful framework for examining how exposure to the workplace and upbringing influence decision-making. In doing so, this study provides useful insights for management education that aims to produce future leaders who are both emotionally intelligent and rationally based.

Jung's Four Functions of Personality Theories:

Carl Jung's psychological types theory shows concern for the conscious usage of purposes of observation in addition to decision-making and the extents of life in which these purposes are used. There are four functions, which include feeling, thinking, sensation, and intuition.

- **Feeling** - involves personal assessment of practices in emotions like hate, love, and pity. It is the process of valuing or sensing. The function of feeling must be eminent from the reaction. The feeling is the assessment of each sensible action. Many of the assessments have no emotional content, but they can become exciting if their concentration rises to the fact of motivating physiological changes inside an individual. Any of the four functions' strength could be increased if the emotions are led⁽¹⁾.
- **Thinking** - denotes cognitive processes and involves the logical and reasonable understanding of remembrance; subsequently, it obtains meaning. Reliant on the person's fundamental attitude, the type of thinking type can also be extraverted or introverted.

Thinking (T)	Making decisions is a function of thinking and feeling. This measures rational and immediate decisions based on received facts from their intuition and sensing. The individuals who prefer thinking measure their decisions by considering some facts, like casual, logical, consistent, and reasonable. Whereas the individual who prefers feeling measures the conclusion by connecting with the circumstances, looking at the situation by depth, and also seeing the requirements of the individual elaborately. Usually, individuals who are thinkers ensure not to adjust or are not comfortable with the illogical people. They are always concerned with truth.
-Feeling (F)	

Thinking (T) vs. Feeling (F)

As per the researchers,⁽²⁾ the characteristics and their measure of the quality of their composition method consist of solving the set of partitioning problems based on the enumeration of all other probable team patterns. Numerous mathematical models are used for balancing Master of Business Administration student teams, which are used to measure the distances, while the results expected are not different but can be effective and efficient to design various kinds of balanced MBA students' teams. In conventional management thinking, constraints are seen as an objectionable barrier to the implementation of ideas and generation for a designer; constraints are comprised as the motivation for creating new solutions. Grades of several MBA students act as an essential requirement, and as a screening device to consider it further. Nowadays, design thinking is more attracted to employers who are interested in customer focus, and innovation. The characteristics, process, and components of

Fig 1. Thinking Vs. Feeling [Source: Prepared based on the Literature Review]

design thinking required to be stated in spoken, and written extensively on the subject of integrative thinking need elaboration, and integrative thinking relationship among the design.

A research on personality type and the "decision-making process" together with the manager's presumptuous verdict preferences (T-F) to influence decision making was conducted by⁽³⁾. The study has come to the important conclusion that all four functions can influence the decision-making process. Despite this data, it has been shown that those with an intuitive and thinking inclination make better decisions than those with superior sensing and feeling. An intuitive person was more likely to seek out knowledge and develop creative, integrative solutions to issues.

Research by⁽⁴⁾ examined the psychological characteristics of early-stage organizational leaders who were thought to be mostly ESTJ profiles. The ESTJ profile of the group of leaders who participated in the current study identified the following traits in connection to responsible leadership: extroverted personalities are seen as energetic and enthusiastically interacting with others. Strong Thinking-Judging inclinations suggest that the STJ personality types place a high value on logical order and structures in the organization and its processes, as well as on accomplishing organizational goals. They also value competence, realism, and cost-efficiency in the use of funds, and they are actively focused on handling immediate concerns.

⁽⁵⁾ did a study to examine decision making concerning cognitive styles, and personality types of Business students. To study this a total of 130 students of post-graduation in the management field were opted using secondary sampling. Decision-making style inventory test (Rowe, and Mason), MBTI (Myers Briggs), and cognitive style inventory by Jha were used to do study. Results concluded relation intuitive personality type, and conceptual conclusion style. Thinking personality type presented a positive correlation with the ruling decision style whereas undesirable with behavioral decision style. An optimistic correlation with behavioral decision style can be seen by feeling personality. Judging personality shows an analytical decision style while perceiver shows inverse relation with it. The study also states the requirement of training on decision making for the students.

In order to identify the current state of market demands for business studies students and to identify the components of employability, a study was conducted on the elements influencing management students' employability abilities⁽⁶⁾. The findings revealed that the most important factors are communication, leadership, work culture, critical thinking ability, and the ability to ask questions. According to the survey, management schools should start offering demanding training and workshop programs to educate students about the current market demands and needs of varied managers from different regions.

2 Methodology

2.1 Problem Statement

Instead of personality characteristics, which change over time, personality types relate to the psychological categorization of diverse individual groups. Still, little is known about the development and interpretation of personality profiles designed

expressly for management students. A generalized model of personality preferences emphasizes the need of taking into account other potential antecedent circumstances that might have an impact on personality profiles. To further comprehend and determine a person's whole personality profile, this entails looking at the many personality types, their origins, and the ways in which demographic factors influence personality preferences.

2.2 Model of Research

Fig 2. Model of Research Variables

2.3 Research Scope

This research looks at a particular predilection for bipolar personalities and compares how dominant each is in comparison to the other. In order to evaluate personality profiles and investigate their connections with demographic data, it focuses on the perceiving function, more especially the **Thinking (T) -Feeling (F)** personality dimensions.

2.4 Objectives

- To assess the psychological characteristics of management students from particular Gujarati business schools, paying particular attention to their capacity to understand the psychological elements of Thinking (T) and Feeling (F).
- To investigate the connection between different management students' demographic characteristics and the personality dimensions of Thinking (T) and Feeling (F).

2.5 Method

In order to investigate the Thinking (T) and Feeling (F) personality characteristics among MBA students of Gujarat state, this study used a **cross-sectional descriptive methodology**. Using a cluster sampling technique, 1,067 first- and second-year students were chosen, ensuring participation from a variety of business schools around the state.

The survey instrument was split into two parts: Section II collected demographic data, while Section I used the NERIS Type Explorer® Scale to evaluate personality traits. With a **Cronbach's Alpha score of 0.87**, which indicates strong internal consistency, the scale's dependability was confirmed.

2.6 Data Analysis Method

Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, frequencies, and percentages) were employed to evaluate the data in order to identify broad patterns. Chi-square tests of independence were used to investigate relationships between personality characteristics (thinking or feeling) and categorical demographic factors (e.g., gender, parental education, and previous work experience).

For this research, the chi-square test is especially appropriate as it aids in determining if two category variables have a statistically significant relationship. It was used to assess if there were significant differences in the distribution of Thinking vs. Feeling qualities among several groups, including gender, previous job experience, and parental education.

Furthermore, ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) was employed to determine if personality trait ratings across several groups (e.g., years of experience, areas, and educational qualifications) differed statistically significantly. When comparing the means of more than two groups, an ANOVA is a suitable test to determine whether there is a significant difference between at least one group. The purpose of this study was to determine if the average propensity for Thinking or Feeling qualities differed among various demographic groups.

2.7 Research Gap and Novel Contributions

This research distinguishes itself from earlier studies that predominantly examine personality traits within confined academic contexts or depend on generalized personality frameworks. It employs a more holistic and statistically robust methodology by incorporating demographic and socio-cultural elements into the analysis of personality. By utilizing cluster sampling across various business schools in Gujarat, this study achieves a broader representation than previous research, which often concentrates on a single institution. Furthermore, while earlier studies typically rely on basic frequency distributions, this research applies sophisticated statistical methods, including Chi-square tests and ANOVA, thereby enhancing the credibility of its findings. A significant innovation of this study is its investigation into the impact of maternal education and prior job experience on the development of Thinking (T) versus Feeling (F) traits, a dimension that has been largely neglected in existing literature. Additionally, rather than simply classifying students into personality categories, this research offers practical recommendations for management education, promoting a balanced integration of emotional intelligence and logical reasoning skills to better equip students for leadership positions in evolving business landscapes.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Analysis of the NERIS Type Explorer® Questionnaire

Objective – 1: To assess the Personality Profiles of management students of selected B- Schools of Gujarat.

To achieve the above-stated objective, Frequency, Percentage, Mean and Standard Deviation of Personality Dimensions were calculated.

Table 1. Average and Standard Deviation of Statements Related to T | F Personality Dimensions

Sr. No.:	Statement	Mean	SD
1	Winning a debate matters less than not making anyone upset	3.49	1.77
2	Urge to justify yourself to other people	3.48	1.72
3	Difficult to relate to other’s feelings	4.09	1.83
4	A quick change in moods	3.42	1.85
5	Truth is important than sensitivities	3.08	1.70
6	No worries about how your actions affect others	3.91	1.89
7	Preferring to see a child grow up a kind than smart	3.28	1.74
8	Don’t let others influence actions	3.31	1.61
9	Emotions control you more than you controlling them	3.64	1.83
10	Difficult to fire devoted but underachieving workers	3.52	1.62
11	Logic is generally more central than the heart	3.02	2.00
12	Offer emotive care than advising ways to deal with the problem	3.42	1.85
13	Being right is significant than being supportive	3.46	1.77
14	Everyone’s opinions are to be respected irrespective of if they are reinforced by facts or not	3.18	1.68
15	Believe in pleasing others than to be powerful	3.42	1.68

The variables’ mean scores, as shown in Table 1, vary from 3.02 to 4.09 (on a scale of 7). It states that every factor taken into account for the study has a significant impact on the personality evaluation. Furthermore, on a scale of 7 to 2, the Standard Deviation (SD) falls between 1.61 and 2.00. This is a relatively high number that reflects the wide range of answers provided by research participants. A high standard deviation might be interpreted as indicating that people’s personality characteristics vary. Every person is unique in their behaviour, attitude, way of thinking, how they make decisions, and how they handle stress.

Fig 3. Distribution of Personality Dimensions (T vs. F) Among Management Students

When the Management Students of B- Schools of Gujarat were asked to reveal the extent to which they value sentiments or rationality more when considering options. An individual tends to use the Thinking (T) personality trait or the Feeling (F) trait, it is evident from the Figure 3, 62.9 percent (671) of the respondents have **Feeling (F)** personality dimensions. As the dominating personality trait among respondents is **Feeling (F)**, a high percentage of management students in Gujarat tend to follow their emotions and sentiments.

They are more kind, empathetic, and whole-hearted compared to 37.1 percentage (396) of Thinking (T) personality dimension respondents, who tend to be objective information, gather the facts, and assess the alternatives contrary to logic and purpose to understand the most effective and realistic decision.

Significant trends in the Thinking (T) and Feeling (F) personality characteristics among Gujarati management students are seen in Table 2. The research reveals that the Feeling (F) attribute is more common in male students (62.3%) than in female students (63.5%), indicating that both genders tend to be more empathetic and make emotional decisions more frequently. Furthermore, pupils who attended vernacular schools also exhibited a higher prevalence of the Feeling (F)

Fig 4. (a-f) Personality Dimensions and Demographic Factors (Professional)

characteristic (62.1%), suggesting that educational background may be a significant factor in determining an individual's emotional orientation in the workplace.

Additionally, individuals seeking undergraduate degrees such as BBA, BCom, B.Tech/B.E, and B.Pharm have a marked inclination towards the Feeling (F) personality trait. This pattern highlights the trait's pervasive effect in a range of academic fields. Additionally, students majoring in human resource management show a strong preference for the Feeling (F) dimension, which is consistent with the interpersonal and compassionate requirements that are present in the HR industry. Taken together, these outcomes highlight the importance of emotional intelligence in the workplace and imply that disciplinary and instructional settings may have a big impact on management students' personality orientations.

Table 2. Cross Tabulation of Personality Dimensions and Demographic Variables (Family)

Variable	Thinking (T)		Feeling (F)		Variable	Thinking (T)		Feeling (F)		
	F	%	F	%		F	%	F	%	
	Family Size (No. of Family Members)					House Type				
1-3	82	36.9	140	63.06	Apartment / Flat	160	36.0	284	64.0	
4-6	270	36.7	466	63.32	Tenement / Bungalow	172	40.0	258	60.0	
7-9	29	37.2	49	62.82	Duplex	53	34.4	101	65.6	
> = 9	15	48.4	16	51.61	Others	11	28.2	28	71.8	
	0	166	38.4	266	61.6		98	35.4	179	64.6
No. of Female Siblings	1-2	202	36.9	346	63.1	No. Male of Siblings	253	37.9	415	62.1
	3 or more	28	32.2	59	67.8		45	36.9	77	63.1
	SSLC	45	31.3	99	68.8		85	42.5	115	57.5
	HSC	70	36.8	120	63.2		80	29.9	188	70.1
Father's Education	Grad-ua-tion	201	37.5	335	62.5	Mother's Education	165	36.8	283	63.2
	Post-Graduation	69	39.7	105	60.3		56	44.4	70	55.6
	Oth-ers	11	47.8	12	52.2		10	40.0	15	60.0

A number of noteworthy patterns are shown when personality characteristics and demographic factors are cross-tabulated. Smaller families (1-3 people) seem to exhibit a larger predisposition toward the Feeling dimension (63.06%), yet this preference is prevalent across all family sizes, suggesting that family size has a consistent effect. Additionally, there is a strong correlation between parental education and personality traits, especially in homes where one or both parents have a master's degree or beyond. For example, the Feeling dimension is more prevalent in the 62.5% of people whose fathers have a college degree, and this pattern is also seen with greater mother education levels. Housing style also seems to matter; people who live in duplex homes have a greater percentage of Feeling types (65.6%), whereas people who live in flats have a more evenly distributed mix of Thinking and Feeling personality orientations. These results imply that personality traits are influenced by family structure as well as socioeconomic variables like living environment and schooling.

Objective -2: To assess the factors affecting the personality of management students.

To investigate the connection between personality traits and demographic variables, a chi-square test of independence was used.

Given that the p-values for the variables listed below are less than 0.05, a significant correlation has been discovered between: Chi-Square test resulted in identifying a significant relationship between **Thinking (T) /Feeling (F) Personality Traits** and

- Gender (p-value - 0.050, df - 1)
- Mother's Education (p-value - 0.021, df - 4)

Table 3. Demographic Factors and Personality Aspects' Association

Variable	Variable * T/F	Variable	Variable * T/F
Gender (1)	0.050	Place (14)	0.425
Age (2)	0.460	Year of Study (1)	0.219
Medium of Instruction in School (2)	0.814	Specialization / Plan (3)	0.420
Educational Qualification (5)	0.315	Prior Job Experience (5)	0.254
Institute / University (28)	0.045		

Table 4. Personality Traits and Family Demographics

Variable	Variable * T/F	Variable	Variable * T/F
Family Size (3)	0.626	Mother's Education (4)	0.021
No. of Male Siblings (2)	0.769	Father's Occupation (5)	0.714
No. of Female Siblings (2)	0.538	Mother's Occupation (5)	0.119
Religion (6)	0.086	Monthly Family Income (3)	0.485
Father's Education (4)	0.437	Type of House (3)	0.313

Note: The Values in the parentheses indicate Degrees of Freedom

3.2 Assessment Personality Dimensions Concerning Regions

To identify the significant difference among the respondents across regions, the ANOVA test was applied. The results for the same is mentioned in the Table 5.

Table 5. Difference in Personality Dimensions Concerning Various Factors

Variables		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regions	Between Groups	595.52	4	148.88	2.12	0.076
	Within Groups	74528.49	1062	70.17		
Educational Qualification	Between Groups	696.36	5.00	139.27	1.99	0.08
	Within Groups	74427.66	1061.00	70.15		
Area of Specializations	Between Groups	210.32	3	70.11	0.99	0.394
	Within Groups	74913.70	1063	70.47		
Religion	Between Groups	653.48	6	108.91	1.55	0.159
	Within Groups	74470.54	1060	70.26		
Father's Education	Between Groups	49.09	4	12.27	0.17	0.952
	Within Groups	75074.93	1062	70.69		
Mother's Education	Between Groups	851.46	4	212.87	3.04	0.017
	Within Groups	74272.56	1062	69.94		
Medium of Instructions in Schools	Between Groups	237.53	2	118.77	1.692	0.185
	Within Groups	73823.95	1052	70.17		
Number of Years of Prior Experiences	Between Groups	786.29	5	157.26	2.244	0.048
	Within Groups	74337.73	1061	70.06		

Table 5 presents an ANOVA analysis of the **Thinking (T) / Feeling (F)** personality dimension across various factors (e.g., Regions, Educational Qualification, etc.). Here are five key interpretations:

- **Regions:** There is no statistically significant difference in Thinking/Feeling between areas ($p > 0.05$), as indicated by the F-value of 2.12 and p-value (Sig.) of 0.076. It appears from lacking statistical significance that students' geographic backgrounds in Gujarat have little bearing on whether they are Thinking or Feeling. This suggests that management students typically have comparable personality traits throughout the state, notwithstanding regional cultural or socioeconomic variations. Therefore, there is no need for regional customization when it comes to the consistent use of educational methodologies for personality development throughout areas.

- **Educational Qualification:** With a p-value of 0.08 and an F-value of 1.99, there appears to be no noticeable variation in personality traits according to educational background ($p > 0.05$). According to this finding, a student's undergraduate degree—such as a BBA, B.Com, or B.Tech—does not substantially affect their propensity for Thinking or Feeling qualities. Practically speaking, students tend to have comparable emotional or rational inclinations regardless of their backgrounds in technology, pharmacy, or business. This implies that personal, experiential, or family variables may have a greater effect on personality traits like decision-making style than academic discipline.
- **Mother's Education:** Based on the mother's level of education, there is a statistically significant difference in Thinking/Feeling ($p < 0.05$), as indicated by the F-value of 3.04 and p-value of 0.017. Here, a statistically significant correlation was found, confirming the idea that personality characteristics are significantly influenced by mother education. Students that have more educated mothers seem to make more logical and analytical decisions, which may lead to a larger application of Thinking (T) qualities. This emphasizes the formative effect of the mother's educational background and is consistent with previous studies on the impact of parents on cognitive development.
- **Number of Years of Prior Experience:** The F-value is 2.244 with a p-value of 0.048, showing that prior experience significantly impacts the Thinking/Feeling dimension ($p < 0.05$). This noteworthy finding implies that students are more likely to exhibit Thinking (T) qualities if they have more job experience. Students may acquire more methodical, analytical approaches to problem-solving when they are exposed to the actual world. This lends credence to the idea that future managers develop rational decision-making abilities via real-world work experience.
- **Other Factors:** No significant differences were observed in Thinking/Feeling dimensions based on the area of specialization, religion, father's education, or medium of instruction, as their p-values are greater than 0.05. The lack of significant results ($p > 0.05$) for these factors suggests that they have little effect on students' preference for Thinking or Feeling modes. For example, although it is reasonable to assume that specializations such as Human Resources would favor Feeling qualities, the findings indicate that these differences are not statistically significant in the general population. This may suggest that personal preferences go beyond cultural indicators such as religion or academic specialty.

Dominance of Feeling (F) Personality Dimension: When it came to personality dimensions, the survey showed that 62.9% of respondents associated with Feeling (F) and 37.1% with Thinking (T). This implies that while making decisions, the majority of Gujarati management students are inclined to give emotions and empathy top priority. This demonstrates that most Gujarati MBA candidates base their decisions on feelings and social factors, which has consequences for the region's management decision-making practices.

Gender Influence: Management students, both male and female, had a greater propensity to adopt the Feeling (F) personality trait—62.3% of males and 63.5% of females, respectively. This indicates that there isn't many gender-based distinctions in thinking or feeling preferences, with both groups tending toward making emotional decisions. The results show that both male and female management students in Gujarat have a comparable propensity for emotional decision-making, in contrast to some previous research that suggested more pronounced gender-based variations in decision-making preferences.

Educational Influence: The Thinking/Feeling dimension and educational background did not significantly differ from one another. The preference for Feeling (F) was somewhat greater among management students specializing in Human Resource (HR) compared to those studying Marketing or Finance, supporting the notion that HR professionals are more likely to consider empathy and interpersonal factors when making decisions.

Family and Parental Influence: The Thinking/Feeling personality factor was strongly impacted by the mother's education ($p = 0.017$). It appears that maternal education influences cognitive decision-making styles since students with moms with greater levels of education tended to display more Thinking (T) features.

Prior Experience: The Thinking/Feeling component was strongly affected by prior job experience ($p = 0.048$). More seasoned professionals tended to lean more toward the Thinking (T) personality characteristic, which values reason and making sense-based decisions. While students with seven or more years of work experience shifted toward the Thinking (T) personality dimension, students with no work experience tended to display the Feeling (F) attribute. This implies that exposure to the actual world and professional obligations support the growth of rational, impartial decision-making skills.

4 Discussion

Emotional Decision-Making Dominates: Given the large proportion of students exhibiting the Feeling (F) component, Gujarat's future managers are probably going to take empathy, feelings, and personal values into account while making choices. This may suggest that in order to improve organizational outcomes, management schools should teach their students how to balance rational and emotional approaches to decision-making.

Minimal Gender Differences: The results of this study show that, contrary to some research suggesting gender differences in cognitive processing, both males and females in management education have a tendency to give emotional elements precedence over logical thinking. This throws into question long-held beliefs about decision-making processes based on gender and advocates for gender-neutral methods in management education. This gender-to-gender convergence points to a cultural leveling effect in which common socialization, upbringing, and perhaps even institutional teaching methods supersede conventional gender-based cognitive disparities. Deeper insights may be obtained from additional study examining the curricula, classroom dynamics, and value systems ingrained in these institutions.

Impact of Mother's Education: The strong correlation found between personality characteristics and the mother's educational background supports the idea that early emotional environments and upbringing shape cognitive choices. Greater propensity toward the Thinking (T) component was shown by students whose mothers had better educational backgrounds, indicating that exposure to organized reasoning and intellectual conversation at home may promote more analytical thinking.

Work Experience Encourages Logical Thinking: The observation that those with more years of work experience score higher on the Thinking (T) dimension implies that exposure to professional settings on the job promotes logical, fact-based decision-making. This supports the pragmatic premise that exposure to responsibility, performance standards, and real-world business choices fosters rational thinking and impartial evaluation. Thus, in order to develop this talent in students who have less professional expertise, educational institutions should think about incorporating real-world experiences.

Implications for Management Education: This study highlights the need for a more comprehensive approach, as the majority of conventional management programs place a strong emphasis on analytical reasoning, quantitative modeling, and data-driven decision-making. Future managers' preponderance of feeling attributes indicates the increasing necessity of including emotional intelligence into leadership development. Management programs and business schools can react by:

- **Integrating Training in Emotional Intelligence:** Core leadership modules should include courses on emotional control, empathy, conflict resolution, and cultural awareness.
- **Combining Role-Playing with Case Analysis:** Role-plays and introspective exercises help improve emotional and interpersonal awareness, while case studies foster critical thinking and reasoning.
- **Customized Learning Paths:** Based on the personality profiles of their students, institutions may think about creating learning interventions. Students with a strong Feeling orientation, for example, can benefit from organized logic-building activities, whereas Thinking-oriented kids might be exposed to leadership challenges that are motivated by empathy.
- **Peer learning and mentoring** can assist close these cognitive gaps early in a student's career by matching them with mentors who can help them strike a balance between emotion and reason.

This study emphasizes how crucial it is to develop leaders who are not just emotionally intelligent but also analytically astute, able to make deliberate choices that are consistent with corporate logic and human values. By doing this, students may be better prepared for the complex, people-driven realities of the workplace through management education.

5 Conclusion

This research examined the Thinking (T) and Feeling (F) personality dimensions in a sample of 1,067 MBA students from different business schools in Gujarat. The analysis utilized the NERIS Type Explorer® Scale (Cronbach's Alpha = 87%) along with sophisticated statistical techniques, including Chi-square tests and ANOVA. The results reveal that 62.9% of the students display the Feeling (F) trait, whereas 37.1% shows the Thinking (T) trait, indicating that a significant portion of management students favors emotional decision-making over logical reasoning.

The study is restricted by a focus on management students from certain business schools of Gujarat state of India, which can limit to the extent the results can be applied to other geographies or groups. Furthermore, because the study uses self-reported data, respondents' assessments of their personality characteristics may be biased. Determining the causal relationship between personality characteristics and demographic variables is further limited by the cross-sectional methodology. Future studies might gain a more thorough grasp of the Thinking (T) and Feeling (F) personality traits in a variety of circumstances by broadening the sample to include students from different fields or geographical areas. To monitor how personality traits, change over time and in reaction to different academic or professional experiences, longitudinal studies might also be carried out.

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